

9th
ANNUAL REPORT
for the year ending June 30, 1965

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

9th
ANNUAL REPORT
for the year ending June 30, 1965

COUNCIL
ON
LIBRARY
RESOURCES,
INC.

1028 Connecticut Avenue, N.W. Washington, D. C. 20036

*PUPITRE D'UNE FACON
particuliere & très commode pour les gens
d'étude.*

PLANCHE LXXXVI. FIGURE 123.

DAns le livre que Rameley a donné au public , on voit une Machine pour le même usage ; mais elle est beaucoup plus composée , plus embarrassante , & par conséquent plus difficile à executer , & plus sujette à se detraquer ; au lieu que celle que je propose ici , est des plus simples.

L'une & l'autre peuvent servir aux personnes , qui s'attachent à l'étude , & qui composent ; principalement à ceux qui sont incommodés de la goutte ; car par le moien de cette Machine , vous pouvez sans changer de place & sans bouger de vôtre fauteuil , lire successivement plusieurs livres les uns après les autres & bien loin d'avoir la peine de les aller chercher , ou de vous les faire apporter , vous les faites facilement venir à vous.

Les deux grandes rouës *A. B.* sont solidement attachées l'une à l'autre par l'axe *C.* qui les fait tourner ensemble sur les pieds droits *D.* Entre ces deux grandes rouës , & au tour de leur circonférence , il y a les tablettes ou pupitres *E.* qui y sont retenus par les especes d'axes coudeés *F.* Ces sortes d'axe coudeés sont mouvans dans les grandes rouës , en sorte que lorsque les rouës tournent , le poids des pupitres les tient toujours dans la même situation , & les empêche de basculer & de perdre leur équilibre.

Avant que de travailler, vous rangez sur les pupitres *E.* tous les Livres dont vous jugez que vous aurez besoin. Ensuite vous étant placé dans le fauteuil *G.* vous lisez le Livre qui se presente d'abord à vous ; & lorsque vous en voulez un autre , vous le faites facilement venir à la place du premier , en tournant avec la main les grandes rouës *A. B.*

Si vos Livres se rencontrent de différente grandeur ou gros-seur , & que tous les plus pesans se trouvent rangez d'un côté , & les plus legers de l'autre ; le fort emportant le foible , vôtre Machine basculera toujours , & vous ne la pourrez pas contenir commodement dans la situation que vous souhaitez. Ainsi pour obvier à cela on pourra ajoûter l'arrêt *H.* qui entrera dans les petites entailles de la grande rouë *A.* & qui la retiendra au point convenable, tant que vous ne voudrez point changer de Livre ; mais qui lui laissera cependant la liberté de tourner , lorsque pour le lacher , vous appuyerez le pied sur la detente *I.*

A la place de la Machine que nous venons de decrire , vous pouvez ranger vos Livres au tour d'une grande table ronde , que vous ferez construire , de maniere que son dessus puisse tourner sur un pivot ; ce qui se fera facilement , en plaçant le pivot au centre de vôtre table sur un de ses piliers , & en garnissant les autres piliers qui soutiennent sa circonférence de petites roulettes. Par ce moien qui est très simple , lorsque vous aurez suffisamment lû le Livre , qui sera devant vous , & que vous en souhaitez un autre , vous le ferez facilement venir à la place du premier , en tournant la table avec la main.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

*Members of the
Council and
Members of the
Board of Directors*

LYMAN H. BUTTERFIELD

*Editor-in-Chief, Adams Papers
Massachusetts Historical Society*

GILBERT W. CHAPMAN *

President, The New York Public Library

VERNER W. CLAPP

President, Council on Library Resources, Inc.

FRED C. COLE

President, Washington and Lee University

JAMES S. COLES

President, Bowdoin College

FREDERICK HARD

President Emeritus, Scripps College

CARYL P. HASKINS *

President, Carnegie Institution of Washington

JOSEPH C. MORRIS

Vice-President, Tulane University

PHILIP McC. MORSE

*Professor of Physics
Massachusetts Institute of Technology*

WHITNEY NORTH SEYMOUR

Partner, Simpson Thacher & Bartlett

FREDERICK H. WAGMAN

*Director of the University Library
University of Michigan*

HERMAN B WELLS

Chancellor, Indiana University

LOUIS B. WRIGHT

Director, Folger Shakespeare Library

* Mr. Chapman was succeeded as a Member of the Council by Dr. Haskins on April 17, 1965.

COMMITTEES AND OFFICERS

Executive Committee

WHITNEY NORTH SEYMOUR, *Chairman*
VERNER W. CLAPP
JAMES S. COLES *
JOSEPH C. MORRIS *
HERMAN B WELLS
LOUIS B. WRIGHT

Finance Committee

WHITNEY NORTH SEYMOUR, *Chairman*
VERNER W. CLAPP
FRED C. COLE

Committee on the Laboratory

JOSEPH C. MORRIS, *Chairman*
JAMES S. COLES
GILBERT W. KING
Director of Research
Itek Corporation
PHILIP McC. MORSE
JOHN R. PIERCE
Director of Research, Communication Principles
Bell Telephone Laboratories, Inc.

Committee on Program

FRED C. COLE, *Chairman*
HERMAN B WELLS
LOUIS B. WRIGHT

Officers

GILBERT W. CHAPMAN **
WHITNEY NORTH SEYMOUR, *Chairman* **
LOUIS B. WRIGHT, *Vice-Chairman*
VERNER W. CLAPP, *President*
MELVILLE J. RUGGLES, *Vice-President*
ELIZABETH OAKES, *Treasurer*
MELVILLE J. RUGGLES, *Secretary - Assistant Treasurer*

Senior Staff Members

LEE E. GROVE, *Director of Publications*
LAURENCE B. HEILPRIN, *Physicist*
ROBERT T. JORDAN, *Library Specialist*

* Dr. Morris was succeeded as a Member of the Executive Committee by President Coles on April 17, 1965.

** Mr. Chapman was succeeded as Chairman by Mr. Seymour on April 17, 1965.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

Late in 1960 the Ford Foundation approved a new grant of eight million dollars to enable the Council to continue for an additional seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems, and at the same time further to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel.

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

INTRODUCTION

Automation in Libraries. Last year's report recorded the publication of the report by Dr. Gilbert W. King and his colleagues of the possibilities of automating the operations of the Library of Congress and of the potential effects of such automation upon the work of the research libraries of the country.¹

Events in the development of library automation subsequently crowded upon each other; yet the essential element for rapid progress in this area is still lacking, in spite of the Council's attempts to hasten its availability — namely, a source of current cataloging information in a standardized machine-readable form.

The early weeks of 1964, in which the King Committee report was published, saw also the publication of the first issue of the *Index Medicus* to be prepared by the National Library of Medicine with computer assistance under the Medlars program. This was an extraordinary achievement, only slightly dimmed by the fact that, because the photocomposing machine with which the system was designed to operate was not at first available, the output of the computer and consequently the typography of the publication were for a while limited to the 56 upper case characters of a line printer. But by the time that the August 1964 issue of the *Index* was to be prepared for the press it could avail itself of the full 226-character font of the photocomposing device. Only so recently has automated printing with a full font been available for bibliographical work!

By the end of the calendar year 1964, too, still other methods were at hand for making the work of the computers typographically suitable for library purposes. By contrast, though not as elaborate as the photocomposition machines with their character sets numbering hundreds or even thousands of separate sorts, the 120-character chain printers marked an enormous

¹ Gilbert W. King and others: *Automation and the Library of Congress. A survey sponsored by the Council on Library Resources, Inc.* Washington: Library of Congress, 1963 [i.e., 1964]. 88 p. See also Robert M. Hayes, Ralph H. Parker and Gilbert W. King: *Automation and the Library of Congress: Three Views*, *The Library Quarterly* 34: 229-239, July 1964; Gilbert W. King: *The Library of Congress Project*, *Library Resources & Technical Services* 9: 90-93. Winter 1965.

advance over the upper-case-only printing devices which since the nineteen-thirties had formed a principal obstacle to the effective application of the automatic data-processing machines to library work. Early significant library projects in which the chain printers were employed were the author, title and subject catalogs in book form with which the library of Florida Atlantic University welcomed its first class of students in the fall of 1964, and the similar catalogs prepared by the Library of the University of Toronto for the Ontario New Universities project early in 1965. Meanwhile, in numerous projects elsewhere, libraries have been applying computers to less typographically demanding tasks, such as order lists, union lists of serials, serial records, circulation records, et cetera, making use of the traditional automated print-out in upper case.

The year saw the publication of several works on various aspects of library automation to which the Council had contributed. The report of the Airlie conference on libraries and automation which had been held in May 1963 appeared in October 1964.² The final published report of the Bolt Beranek and Newman inquiry into prospects and problems of libraries of the future was published in March 1965.³ Together with the King report these publications contributed to the stimulation of active planning of national computer-based informational networks which began in earnest at about this time, and to which reference is made on a later page.

Of course, every library that uses a computer for processing bibliographic data is compelled to effect its own conversion of the data to machine-readable form. Because this is expensive, each library converts only that part of the bibliographic record that is essential for the project in hand. There is no such thing as a common source of machine input of the data, if only for the reason that there is as yet no agreement on a standard format. And the planning of a standard format would have to regard the uses to be expected of the machine record. For example, if printout in both upper and lower case,

² Barbara Evans Markuson, ed.: *Libraries and Automation. Proceedings of the Conference on Libraries and Automation held at Airlie Foundation, Warrenton, Virginia, May 26-30, 1963 under the sponsorship of the Library of Congress, National Science Foundation, Council on Library Resources, Inc.*, Washington, D. C. Library of Congress, 1964. 268 p.

³ J. C. R. Licklider: *Libraries of the Future*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, The M. I. T. Press [1965]. 219 p.

both Latin and Greek characters, both regular and boldface type were to be possible, the portions of text to be so presented would have to be suitably identified.

Thus, even before the publication of the King Committee report, the most important next task seemed to the Council to be to encourage the development of a format of conversion of bibliographic data to machine-readable form capable of meeting all foreseeable bibliographic and typographic needs and of providing a basis for acceptance sufficient for initiating the development of a current source of supply of bibliographic information suitable for machine processing. A contract was placed with Inforonics, Inc. (a firm that combines experience in automated preparation of catalog cards with accomplishment in the development of computer-controlled typesetting and photocomposition programs) to develop such a format, working with the staff of the Library of Congress. The report of this study, rendered in November 1964, was given general distribution following its discussion in a meeting sponsored by the Library of Congress and the Committee on Automation of the Association of Research Libraries in January 1965.⁴

The way seemed open to demonstrate the conversion procedure by applying it to a corpus of bibliographic data. At that moment an interesting body of such data presented itself in the form of approximately 65,000 entries of the "California List" of books suitable for college libraries prepared at the University of California at San Diego in preparation for the opening of libraries on three new campuses. It was desirable that this list should be published in book form, and the American Library Association was interested in doing this. If now the catalog entries for the books cited by the list should be converted to machine-readable form, important experience could be gained in processing the data — in sorting and arranging the entries, in extracting from them the parts appropriate for a book-form catalog, in further extracting personal names and subject entries to make an index, and in controlling a printing, typesetting or photocomposing machine to prepare the printer's copy. In addition, the machine record would be available for still other programs, and for inexpensive interfiling and updating.

⁴ Lawrence F. Buckland: *The Recording of Library of Congress Bibliographical Data in Machine Form*. Maynard, Massachusetts: Inforonics, Inc., 1964. Revised, February 1965. Washington: Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1965. x, 54 p.

Before this attractive project could be undertaken, estimates of the costs of converting the data to machine form, and of the computer programs that would be needed, as well as certain decisions with respect to the arrangements of the machine record, needed to be made. To procure this information the Library of Congress contracted for a further study by Inforonics, Inc., underwritten by the Council, but at the close of the fiscal year the study was not completed.

Solving the Problems of Libraries. When the Council was established in 1956 it was the only agency exclusively concerned with assisting toward the solution of the problems of libraries. It is no longer so. In 1961 a Library Research Center was established at the University of Illinois to conduct applied research in the public library field. During the past year the University of California activated the Institute of Library Research, which, using the numerous libraries of the University and campuses of the University as a laboratory, proposes to conduct research into library problems and develop methods for improvement of library work, with emphasis upon the University of California system, and advance education for librarianship. The Institute has commenced work by naming a task force to attack some of the pressing problems of the University's libraries.

In January 1964 the Massachusetts Institute of Technology announced the establishment, effective the following July, of a long range program for the application of the principles and methods of information processing to library operation, with the specific objective of establishing the bases upon which the technical library of the future may be modeled. This activity, which has come into being as Project Intrex (Information Transfer Exchange) during the past year, as its first step planned a five-week conference to explore the problems of library work and to plan an attack upon them.

Within the Federal government, too, there has been a search for solutions for the problems of libraries. The Office of Science Information Service of the National Science Foundation has for a number of years included library-based projects in its program of support; these, of course, by definition have related to the diffusion of scientific information. During the past two years, stimulated by, among other things, the prospect of enormously improved information processing and communi-

cation made possible by computers, several Government agencies have attempted to develop plans for nation-wide information networks. One such plan, which took as its model the Medlars system of the National Library of Medicine, was developed by Dr. Stafford L. Warren, a Special Adviser to the President, and held the attention of the library community for most of the year. More recently, the Committee on Scientific and Technological Information of the Federal Council on Science and Technology has assumed the tasks of developing the outlines of a nationwide network.

The Archival Programs of the States. While, with the exception of the system centering about the *Index Medicus*, mechanization in libraries has thus progressed steadily but unspectacularly during the past year, several significant achievements were effected in other areas of library work.

One of these was the publication in November 1964 of the survey of the archival programs of the 50 states and Puerto Rico, conducted for the Society of American Archivists by Dr. Ernst Posner.⁵ As was pointed out when the Council's grant for this project was made, it was intended to result in no mere academic study but rather to have very practical effects in setting standards of archival management in the states and of stimulating compliance with them.

The response to the publication was both rapid and extensive. In one state which enacted last year two statutes greatly improving the archival program, the archivist has testified that the book was a major factor in the achievement, for not only did the commission which introduced the legislation rely heavily upon it in presenting a report, but the book was an important element in the orientation of the members of the commission to the dimensions of their responsibilities.

So widespread was response of this kind as to justify making a record of its progress at a much earlier stage than might have been thought profitable. Accordingly, a small supplemental grant enabled the Society to assemble a report of developments to the end of the fiscal year. This made possible the summary of progress that appears on a later page.

Preservation of Library Materials. Just as the past year

⁵ Ernst Posner: *American State Archives*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press [1964]. xiv, 397 p.

closed, the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, which investigates for the Council problems relating to the preservation of library materials, sent to the press the report of a study which appears to have been successful in identifying a polyvinyl acetate adhesive, intended for use in "perfect binding," with an almost indefinite longevity. There remains to develop a suitable binding technique in order to convey the advantages of this development to library work, but if this can be done the benefits may be substantial.

In November 1964 a committee of the Association of Research Libraries reported on the assignment which it had undertaken in 1962 to prepare a master plan for the preservation of research library materials in the libraries of the United States. In its report the Committee leaned heavily on preservation procedures developed by the Barrow Laboratory, including aerosol deacidification and storage at low temperatures; the latter, however, is still an hypothesis formed by Mr. Barrow some years ago which the Laboratory is attempting to validate. By the very nature of the case it is difficult to simulate, in the brief time span of a laboratory experiment, the effects of storage over decades and centuries. However, the hypothesis, even though unproven, has been so intuitively persuasive to those who have been exposed to it, especially through the Committee's report, that without waiting for further verification, a number of libraries are already planning cool or cold storage areas.

The Federal Library Committee. The United States Government owns and operates more libraries than any other body in the Western hemisphere. These libraries number many thousands, and present in their diversity a complete spectrum of types of libraries, ranging all the way from great national libraries through university, college, and public libraries to specialized research libraries in subjects as various as law, wood technology, nuclear physics and the fine arts. Yet in spite of their number and of the size of the investment and of the continuous operating cost which they represent, there has been no mechanism in the past for coordinating their work — each has been a law to itself. Although suggested repeatedly at least since 1896 when the librarian of Amherst College urged it upon the Joint Committee on the Library, a council of the Federal libraries did not come into being, principally — it may be presumed — because of the separation of the Govern-

mental libraries in the Executive, Legislative and Judicial establishments.

Last year's report described the renewal of the recommendation for a Federal library council in the report of the survey of Federal libraries conducted for the Brookings Institution by Dr. Luther H. Evans, and it was stated that a genuine effort appeared to be under way to find a formula for carrying the recommendation into effect. Such a formula was found during the past year as the result of discussions between the Library of Congress and the Bureau of the Budget, and on March 11, 1965 the Library announced the formation of a Federal Library Committee of 12 permanent and six rotating members to deal on a Government-wide basis with problems and policies affecting Government libraries.

Summary of Operations in 1965. Twenty-four grants, contracts and other allocations were made by the Council in the amount of \$714,221 in the fiscal year which ended on June 30, 1965. Twenty-one of the allocations were for new projects; three were for extensions or renewals of previously-supported projects.

The following pages briefly describe projects initiated during the past year and results of projects completed.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

I. BIBLIOGRAPHIC APPARATUS AND TECHNIQUES

(The ultimate objective of library work is to put into the hands of a reader a document or source of information responding to his need. The apparatus and techniques by which the appropriate document or information is identified are those of bibliography. The apparatus includes systems of classification, catalogs, indexes and bibliographies of many kinds, including new varieties in the form of punched cards and computers. The techniques include the arts of constructing and of using the apparatus.)

A perceptive English scholar, John Willis Clark, once wrote that "A library may be considered from two very different points of view: as a workshop, or as a Museum. . . . The former," he said, "commends itself to the practical turn of mind characteristic of the present day; common sense urges that mechanical ingenuity, which has done so much in other directions, should be employed in making the acquisition of knowledge less cumbrous and less tedious; that as we travel by steam, so we should also read by steam, and be helped in our studies by the various resources of modern invention."⁶

Though there is not as much travel by steam as there was in 1894, when Clark's book was published, mechanical ingenuity — of a high order — is being used to make the acquisition of knowledge less cumbrous. If the talk of dazzling wonders of mechanization outstrips mechanical performance, if progress seems slow, it is because one must be able to walk before learning to run, and — besides — libraries are complicated organisms, one portion of which, if thrown out of kilter, can bring the whole to confusion and near collapse.

Automation and Bibliography. The principal events of the past year with respect to the progress of automation in libraries

⁶ J. W. Clark, *Libraries in the Medieval and Renaissance Periods. The Rede Lecture, Delivered June 13, 1894.* Cambridge, Macmillan and Bowes, 1894. Further to the above: "There lies on my table at this present moment a *Handbook of Library Appliances*, in which fifty-three closely printed pages are devoted to this interesting subject, with illustrations of various contrivances by which the working of a large library is to be facilitated and brought up to date. In fact, from this point of view, a library may be described as a gigantic mincing-machine, into which the labours of the past are flung, to be turned out again in a slightly altered form as the literature of the present."

have been mentioned in the Introduction. From this account it is once more apparent that such progress is altogether dependent upon the ability of the automatic data processing machines to meet the requirements of bibliographic description, necessarily involving the use of the panoply of typographic symbols which bibliography has pressed into its service over the years. Until such use was made possible, the assistance of automation to library work was perforce restricted, as it has been for many years, to very narrow and specialized applications.

Proceeding directly from this consideration is another. Just as the high cost of home-made cataloging has forced libraries into purchasing a mass-produced article, so the cost of creating a home-made bibliographic record (typically of cataloging information) on which to base library automation is too high for individual institutions. They must, in consequence, be able to benefit from the lower cost of a mass-produced product.

These are the considerations which led the Council during the past year to defer support of projects in library automation which would be found to be premature for want of the necessary conditions, and instead to engage in efforts to hasten the availability of a source of cataloging information in machine-readable form. These efforts have taken the forms described in the Introduction.

Automated Filing. In addition to other projects in automation the Council has engaged in one which is seeking solutions to the problems of automated filing. The automated catalog will of course need to follow filing rules. Now the filing rules used in large libraries are extremely complex. The question must be faced, in consequence, whether and in what respects to simplify them so as to enable the machines to follow them without excessive cost, or whether and in what respects it will be necessary and desirable to pay the costs of requiring the machines to follow them in their present form. As an example, library filing rules generally assume that the abbreviation "St." will file as "Street" or "Saint," as appropriate, the differentiation being determined by the filer. In automated filing, unless no distinction were to be made, the differentiation would have to be supplied by the filing (sorting) program responding to information supplied by the cataloger.

In order to isolate the issues involved in this problem, the

Council during the past year commissioned a study of automating the rules of filing from Inforonics, Inc. simultaneously with the other inquiries placed with this firm. It is expected that the results will be published.

Cataloging Codes. The Council has, beginning in the first year of its existence, contributed in some manner, direct or indirect, to work on the new catalog code of the American Library Association.⁷ Indeed, the Council's very first grant was in the interest of international standardization of cataloging rules. The completion of the ALA Code was deferred until after the International Conference on the Principles of Cataloging, Paris, November 1961. It was then taken up in earnest with the Council's support and with the conscious objective of making a code acceptable for use not only in the United States but by the English-speaking peoples generally. To this end the plan of work has provided for collaboration with the library associations in Great Britain, Canada and elsewhere, and the budget has provided for international travel.

During the past year the plans for the Code were broadened to include rules for non-book materials such as manuscripts, music and sound recordings, but the end was in sight. The Council made what is expected to be a final grant, supplementing contributions by the American Library Association and the Library of Congress.

International Standardization of Rules for the full Cataloging of Music. The International Association of Music Libraries has for several years been drafting an international standard for music cataloging.⁸ Again this past year the Council assisted this effort by contributing the travel expense of the member (Mrs. Virginia Cunningham) charged with preparing the final draft of the rules to the meeting in Dijon where it was approved for publication.

A Shelf Classification for Anglo-American Legal Literature. The desirability of a scheme of shelf-arrangement for legal literature has been discussed in the United States at least since 1885 when it was proposed to the American Bar Association that it sponsor the preparation of such a classification. A number of schemes have been prepared and published since then,

⁷ I: 28; II: 10-11; IV: 13; V: 16; VI: 12-13; VII: 16; VIII: 14. (Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports; in this case to the 1st Annual Report, page 28, etc.)

⁸ VIII: 15.

but none has met with general acceptance for the very simple reason that no central service was available to assume the obligation of applying the scheme to current publications, of making the results known to the libraries which could benefit by it, and of keeping the scheme up to date.

Until recently this was of no great consequence. Law libraries were generally self-arranging by obvious groupings — statutes, digests, reports, et cetera, within jurisdictions — which are easily understood by the user.

Time has changed that. The literature of the law, grown complex with the years, now — like other literatures — requires the assistance of shelf-classification.

In 1958, during the Washington meetings of the American Association of Law Libraries, the Council arranged for discussions on this subject which resulted in a project in which the Library of Congress explored with an advisory body representing the Association and other interested groups the possibility of developing the Library's inchoate Class K (Law) to the point at which its printed catalog cards could contain shelf-classification symbols for legal as for other works. Consensus on a plan, restricting its initial application to Anglo-American Law, was reached early in 1962. In order to speed the execution of the plan and the commencement of the benefits to be derived from it, the Council made another grant to the Library for a two-year project which, it was hoped, would result in the publication of a classification schedule for Anglo-American law and the commencement of the publication of classification assignments for new publications on the printed catalog cards. To this end a project staff was developed, which included the Library's senior subject cataloger in law, Dr. Werner B. Ellinger, and the retiring law librarian of Columbia University, Dr. Miles O. Price, as principal consultant.⁹ By the end of 1964 there had been prepared an approved draft schedule of topics for United States Federal law, supported by a card record of the Library's holdings arranged by topic, while it was planned that the schedule of topics for state law would be developed in analogy to the Federal arrangement. Concurrently, the Library was not only continuing the effort toward the completion and publication of schedules for United States Federal,

⁹ III: 23-25; VI: 18-19.

state and local law (with English law to come later) and toward printing shelf-classification symbols for law on the cards at an early date, but was seeking a Congressional appropriation to speed the process of shelf-classification in its own collections.

Meanwhile the history and theoretical and procedural aspects of the project were the subject of a panel discussion during the 57th Annual Meeting of the American Association of Law Libraries, of which a report has been published.¹⁰

Shared Cataloging. As reported last year, it is estimated that the 74 members of the Association of Research Libraries expend approximately \$18 million annually, amounting to approximately 16 per cent of their budgets, on cataloging, but in spite of this their cataloging arrears increased 160 per cent in the previous decade. Although they use Library of Congress printed catalog cards for as much of their cataloging as possible, these cards meet on the average only 46 per cent of their needs, while the cataloging performed without such cards costs approximately four times as much as that done with them.¹¹

In consequence, the Association has undertaken a study to ascertain whether by sharing the labor, the cataloging process cannot be made more efficient and economical. The first step, for which the Council made a grant in 1964, is to secure data on the original cataloging now being performed in the several libraries through an investigation to be carried on in nine of them. During the past year the Council made a supplementary grant to defray the cost of a meeting of head catalogers of the institutions involved in the investigation.

Alphabetic Subject Indexing. A grant to the University of New South Wales, made late in 1964, is to assist an investigation under the direction of Mr. John Metcalfe, Director of the University's Graduate School of Librarianship, into the principles of alphabetical subject indexing and cataloging.

Mr. Metcalfe, who is the author of two books in the field,¹²

¹⁰ The Library of Congress Classification Schedule for Anglo-American Law. *Law Library Journal* 57: 352-376, November 1964.

¹¹ VIII: 15-16.

¹² John Metcalfe: *Information Indexing and Subject Cataloging*. New York: The Scarecrow Press, Inc., 1957. 388 p. ———: *Subject Classifying and Indexing of Libraries and Literature*. New York: The Scarecrow Press, Inc., 1959. xii, 347 p.

has been sharply critical of the departure from the principles of Charles Ammi Cutter and his successors, including Julius Otto Kaiser. He believes that a return to these principles is possible as well as desirable.¹³ The study proposes not only to justify the basic principles of subject analysis as Mr. Metcalfe believes them to be, but also to rationalize the grammar of subject headings (for example, when should an entry take the form "race horses" and when "horses, racing"?) Because of the lack of grammatical principles and clarity, Mr. Metcalfe believes, basic analytical principles have been subverted. The project is being conducted at the School of Librarianship and the results are to be published.

"Coordinate" Indexing of Legal Literature — Project Lawsearch. The Council has supported several projects having the objective of improving through mechanization the methods for searching legal literature. The mechanization involved in such projects is usually of an institutionalized and expensive kind, typically dependent upon computers. It was the deliberate aim of one project, however, to avoid any technique which would result in removing the mechanism from the direct control of the searcher. This study was known as Project Lawsearch.¹⁴

Project Lawsearch proposed to demonstrate, in the first place, the superiority of "coordinate indexing" as an instrument for searching the literature of the law. (In this form of index the indexing terms are typically limited to single words representing elemental concepts. Searching is conducted by combining terms, thus successively eliminating all documents except those indexed by every term in the combination. A document thus identified can be described as being at the intersection of the Cartesian coordinates representing the several terms — whence the name. It is claimed that much "deeper" indexing can be effected at less cost by "coordinate" than by traditional indexing.)

Besides this, the Project proposed to demonstrate that such an index can be efficiently exploited by a mechanism so simple that, like indexes of traditional form, it can be controlled entirely by the investigator, in contrast to mechanized indexes

¹³ Charles Ammi Cutter: *Rules for a Dictionary Catalog*, 4th ed., Washington, Government Printing Office, 1904. Julius Otto Kaiser: *Systematic Indexing*. London, Sir I. Pitman & Sons, 1911.

¹⁴ V: 16; VI: 19-20; VII: 13-14.

TERMATREX portable card reader with a sliding Read-Out Scale, which can be held in exact position by permanent magnets. The scale makes easier the identification of the coincident holes in the cards, illuminated by light from below, placed in the reader.

TERMATREX information retrieval system. File contains cards each of which represent an indexing term. Holes are drilled in the cards to identify indexed documents. Refinements make possible either alphabetic or random numerical filing.

requiring advanced data processing machines for exploitation.

The Project was developed in discussions with the American Association of Law Libraries which appointed an advisory committee consisting of five university law librarians with Julius Marke of New York University as chairman, other members being Miss Frances Farmer of the University of Virginia, Vincent E. Fiordalisi of Rutgers, J. Myron Jacobstein of Stanford, and Miles O. Price, emeritus, of Columbia.

Work on the experimental index was begun in April, 1961, by a consortium of three law publishers — the Michie Company, Matthew Bender & Company, and the Bureau of National Affairs, Inc., under the direction of William H. B. Thomas, a lawyer to whom the Project owed much of its inspiration. The corpus of legal literature selected for the experiment was the Federal law of motor carriers and consisted of the relevant statutory law and approximately 1700 cases relating to liability of motor carriers.

Meanwhile, Jonker Business Machines, Inc., the manufacturers of an information-retrieval device named Termatex, was developing a form of this device to make possible the inexpensive dissemination and exploitation of the experimental index.

This device consists of 11 x 9.5 inch cards; each card represents an indexing term, while holes in the cards represent documents indexed. When several cards are superimposed over a light table, the holes which coincide are illumined and identify the documents which are indexed by all the terms represented by those cards.

However, not only are the cards bulky, but the expense of updating and replacing them at frequent intervals, as would be required in a legal indexing publication system, would be excessive. Consequently, what was planned for the Project was a microfilm version of the cards, known as Minimatrex. Microfilm copies could be made inexpensively from one master set of the cards, and the master set would be the only one to be continuously updated. The manufacturers were therefore commissioned to construct a special precision camera to reduce the Termatex cards to Minimatrex films, and to devise a simple handviewer for consulting superimposed Minimatrex films. As the latter did not prove feasible, a projector type of viewer was constructed.

When the index was completed in September 1962¹⁵ preparations for testing had already commenced. The first step was to convert the index from printed words in a book to holes in Termatex cards. This was effected mechanically. Tabulating cards were prepared, each card representing a document and one of the terms by which it was indexed. At an average of 30 terms per document, there were more than 50,000 cards in this set. After being mechanically resorted by term, the cards were used to guide the drill which made the holes in the Termatex cards. In the test of the system the full-size cards were used in order not to confuse the test of information-retrieval capability by considerations related to the miniaturization of the equipment.

The test was conducted on four weekends in April and May 1963 in the library of the Association of the Bar of the City of New York under the supervision of the advisory committee. A team consisting of nine experienced law librarians and outstanding third-year law students conducted literature searches on eight questions dealing with the liability of motor carriers, each searcher using conventional methods for four of the questions and the "coordinate" index for the other four. Thus, a total of 72 searches was made, half by each of the two methods. The cases identified were judged for relevance on a scale of four by each member of the committee separately, and the results were then analyzed statistically by Dr. Laurence B. Heilprin of the Council's staff in a report which has been published.¹⁶

This analysis indicates that there was no highly significant difference in retrieval power between the two methods of search; that the probability of an individual searcher discovering a case in point (having the highest degree of relevance) was only approximately 50 per cent by either method even when such cases existed; and that while the "coordinate" index gave a slight overall advantage in search time over the

¹⁵ *Index to the Law of Motor Carriers*. [Washington:] Project Lawsearch, 1962. 5 vols., 28 cm. (Parts I, II and III, Liability for personal injury to passengers. Liability for loss of or injury to goods. [Part IV], The Federal Motor Carrier Act [Secs. 202, 203(b)] and related materials. [Part V], (Addendum.) *Index Data to the Law of Motor Carriers*. [Washington:] Project Lawsearch, 1962, 2 vols., 28 cm.

¹⁶ L. B. Heilprin and S. S. Crutchfield: Project Lawsearch: A Statistical Comparison of Coordinate and Conventional Legal Indexing. *Proceedings of the American Documentation Institute*, 1:215-234 (1964).

conventional system which increased as the test progressed, presumably as the effect of a learning process, yet this advantage disappeared when the searcher was unable to find a case in point.

Thus, the "coordinate" index failed to demonstrate a significant superiority over conventional indexes, in spite of its numerous "access points" and the manipulability of its terms which were expected to provide such a superiority. Nevertheless, the tests did call attention to a number of important matters, such as the 50 per cent probability of discovering a case in point. It is expected that the Advisory Committee, which has been developing its final report in a series of meetings and drafts, will call attention to some of these matters as needing further study.¹⁷

The National Register of Microform Masters. In this record, established during the past year, have converged the results of several efforts previously supported by the Council.

In February 1960 the Council made a grant to the Association of Research Libraries for a study of the bibliographic control of microforms.¹⁸ The investigation was conducted by Professor Wesley Simonton of the University of Minnesota Library School.¹⁹ One of Professor Simonton's recommendations led to a revision of the rules for cataloging microforms. Another recommendation was for the establishment of a national register of microform masters which, by providing information regarding what has been copied in microform, what is currently being copied, and what needs to be copied, would avoid wasteful duplication of effort and discourage piecemeal copying in favor of more carefully planned projects.

The case for coordination of effort in this field was cogently stated in a report prepared by Dr. Lester K. Born under the sponsorship of the American Council of Learned Societies with

¹⁷ See also Frederick Jonker: The New "Termatex" Line of I. R. Systems—The "Minimatex" Line of I. R. Systems. *American Documentation* 14: 276-282, October 1963; Gerald J. Sophar: "Termatex" as a Tool for Storing and Searching Indexes to the Law. *M. U. L. L. (Modern Uses of Logic in Law)* 1-12, June 1964; William H. B. Thomas: Project Lawsearch, A Non-Electronic Approach to Law Searching. *Ibid.* 49-54, March 1963.

¹⁸ IV: 15.

¹⁹ V: 31. Wesley Simonton: *The Bibliographical Control of Microforms, A Report Submitted to the Association of Research Libraries, June 1, 1961.* [Minneapolis, The Author, 1961.] 19 1. Processed. Also in: *Library Resources and Technical Services* 6: 29-40, Winter 1962.

the aid of a grant from the Council.²⁰ It was further emphasized at a conference convened by the Library of Congress in 1961, with assistance from the Council, of representatives of learned societies and research institutions.²¹

Center for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying. The National Register is concerned with the copying of printed material. In another step to implement the recommendations of earlier studies,²² the Library of Congress has, with the assistance of the Council, established a clearinghouse which is expected to contribute to coordination of effort in the photocopying of unpublished foreign source materials for historical research. This clearinghouse is the Center for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying, created during the past summer.

The Center is expected to operate on an experimental basis for three-and-a-half years. It will record the progress, from start to completion, of projects for photocopying foreign archival and manuscript records, and will seek to eliminate duplication of effort by publicizing projects in progress and upon completion. It will seek to develop standards and techniques for the execution and recording of results of projects so as to promote efficiency, assure bibliographical control, and achieve maximum benefit to the scholarly community as a whole. It will inform individuals and groups about copying possibilities and procedures, give technical advice when needed, and assist in the development of cooperative projects. It will also seek to promote mutually advantageous arrangements between domestic and foreign repositories.

The Center will serve, too, as the secretariat for a national committee on the photocopying of foreign manuscript and archival material needed by American investigators. The Committee, which is expected to provide leadership in the field, will be composed of representatives of the various learned societies.

National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. Beginning in 1958 the Council made a series of grants to the Library

²⁰ VIII: 12-13. Planning For Scholarly Photocopying, A Report Prepared For the American Council of Learned Societies. *PMLA* (Publications of The-Modern-Language-Association-of-America) 79: 1-14. September 1964.

²¹ *Conference on Copying European Manuscript Sources for American History, Woodrow Wilson Room, Library of Congress, Friday, April 7, 1961.* 12 p., processed.

²² IV: 17; V: 19, 42; VIII: 22-23.

of Congress for the purpose of establishing this important and long-desired record.²³ The original plans contemplated that the end-product of the undertaking would be a union catalog made up of printed cards, each of which would represent a collection in some repository. Copies of the cards could be obtained by any purchaser, who could with them construct his own union catalog.

What actually resulted was infinitely better. Once the cards were printed it became quite possible to use them for printer's copy for a book-form catalog, produced by photo-offset — much more convenient to use, and costing only a fraction of what a card catalog would have cost. The first two volumes of the catalog, together with an index volume, were published by commercial publishers at no cost either to the Library or to the grant, and at very low prices for such volumes. With the issuance of the second volume in 1964 the descriptions of 12,324 collections in 398 repositories had been published.

But it was clear that the project, once well launched, should be put on a continuing basis. Accordingly, as reported last year, the Library of Congress sought, and in the Legislative Branch Appropriation Act 1965 received a Congressional appropriation with which it has since carried on the work. Meanwhile, the Library has been using unexpended balances from the Council's last grant for the Catalog in promotional work among depository institutions with a view to assuring the completeness of its coverage.

Pre-1956 Files of the National Union Catalog. Beginning with imprints of 1956, reports of holdings of American libraries are published by the Library of Congress in book form—*The National Union Catalog; A Cumulative Author List*. There remain in unique, unpublished, card catalog form some 12 million entries for imprints prior to 1956. The Subcommittee on the National Union Catalog of the Committee on Resources of American Libraries of the American Library Association has long been seeking a way to publish this record. In recent months very real prospects have developed for commercial publication, in some 800-1000 volumes, through photo-offset reproduction of the cards. However, it is estimated that

²³ III: 19-21; VI: 13-14; VII: 8-9; VIII: 9-12.

approximately a million of the cards will have to be retyped to make such reproduction possible.

Just at this time it is becoming increasingly desirable to secure a machine-readable version of this bibliographic record. Such a version might be used to automate searching of the record at a central point, in the transmission of portions of it as required, for duplicating it in whole or part to create regional records, or to automate the typesetting and printing of the catalog. It seemed to the Subcommittee to be useful, before commissioning the retyping of the million entries, to ascertain the costs of creating a machine-readable version.

Accordingly, in March 1965 the Council contracted on behalf of the Subcommittee with the International Business Machines Corporation to take a sample from the pre-1956 record and to estimate from it the characteristics of the entire file in terms of language, number of characters per entry and the cost of making a machine record by various methods.

Catalog Card Reproduction. The reproduction of library catalog cards presents technical difficulties of several kinds. One of these stems from the fact that, if separate proofreading of each card is to be avoided, the cards must be multifolded. But multifolding methods that give results acceptable for card catalogs are typically mass-production methods such as printing by letterpress, the stencil process or offset lithography — processes designed for the production of hundreds or thousands of copies, while the number of cards required (except for large library operations involving many branches) is typically limited to some five to twenty copies.

In addition, whereas the mass products of the press are identical in content, in catalog card reproduction a further step is typically taken by which individual copies are differentiated with filing entries so as to call attention to the book at separate places in the catalog — under the name of the author, the title, various subjects, et cetera. Thus we have the anomalous situation in which a mass-produced item must be individualized before it can be used.

For these reasons, catalog card reproduction is one of the library problems to which the Council has long given attention. Several years ago it supported the efforts of the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association in con-

tracting with George Fry & Associates for a comparative study of the various processes available for the reproduction of catalog cards.²⁴ The study has been completed and a report published.²⁵

This report is intended to give librarians a guide to the selection of a process for reproducing catalog cards suitable to their particular needs. Following a general review, detailed descriptions are given of the equipment and procedures involved in 13 processes for reproducing cards in use in various libraries. These processes range from simple stencil duplication to complex processes such as electrostatic and diffusion-transfer photocopying. The comparative costs of the various processes are indicated and a method is given for making systematic cost comparisons.

In another effort to improve catalog card reproduction the Council, through a contract with Capital Graphics, Inc., investigated the possibilities of using offset lithography for short-run reproduction by using a "waterless" master requiring a less complicated press than ordinary. The possibilities which were identified were not, however, sufficiently promising to justify further investigation.

A Cataloger's Camera. The original cataloger's camera of 1957-8 was to have produced sets of catalog cards, complete with filing entries, by a rapid dry photographic process from any suitable master copy. The camera worked, but for electrical reasons its product failed to meet the graphic arts standards required by library card catalogs.²⁶

There still remained the need for a camera which would reproduce, if not for the catalog then for the cataloger, a catalog entry (e.g., from one of the Library of Congress catalog publications) by a quick dry process so as to expedite the cataloging process. A member of the science publicity staff of Indiana University, Mr. Hugh Hazelrigg, developed a working model of such a camera. Its prospective usefulness has justified the Council in making a small grant for the construction of a production model.

²⁴ VI: 35; VII: 39.

²⁵ *Catalog Card Reproduction*. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, 1965. xii, 82 p. Ill.

²⁶ II: 14; III: 29.

Preparation of a Subject-Heading List Using a Sequential Camera. A previous report has described the project of the Cataloging and Classification Committee of the American Association of Law Libraries for producing a list of legal subject headings, resulting in the publication of a substantial volume in 1963.²⁷ The technique that was adopted for the production of the printer's copy involved, for various reasons, including its contribution to the editing process and its prospective facilitation of future revisions of the list, the use of a sequential camera. Dr. Werner B. Ellinger, the chairman of the Committee responsible for the publication, has now published an article describing this technique.²⁸

Library Science Abstracts. The journal bearing this title, constituting the principal abstracting service in the field of library science, is published by the British Library Association. With a view to promoting its excellence the Council enabled its editor, Mr. H. Allan Whatley, to visit the principal documentation centers in library work and documentation on the European and North American continents.²⁹ During the past year Mr. Whatley completed his survey and rendered a report.

Area Studies for Undergraduates. Lewis and Clark College in Portland, Oregon, conducts a program in which undergraduates are sent to foreign countries for a year's residence, study and work. This program has been handicapped by the lack of bibliographies of the countries concerned which are suitable for undergraduates. As reported last year,³⁰ the Council enabled a member of the faculty, Dr. Hideo Hashimoto, to make a bibliography of materials on Japan. It was thought that this might serve as the pilot compilation in a series and also that it might be of use to other institutions with requirements of this kind. The project has been completed.

²⁷ IV: 15; VII: 14-15, Werner B. Ellinger, ed.: *Subject Headings for the Literature of Law and International Law*. South Hackensack, New Jersey: Published for the American Association of Law Libraries by Fred B. Rothman & Co., 1963. 380 p. (AALL Publications Series No. 6).

²⁸ Werner B. Ellinger: Use of a Sequential Camera for Composition of a List of Subject Headings. *Law Library Journal* 57: 217-223, August 1964.

²⁹ VIII: 17.

³⁰ VIII: 19.

II. PHYSICAL ACCESS

(The bibliographical apparatus is merely a means to an end. Ultimately, the cited manuscript, book or periodical must be seen and consulted, either in its original form or in some acceptable facsimile.)

“*Ease of Access to Archives*”. One of the specific purposes for which the Council was established was to promote liaison and cooperation with foreign libraries and archives. In the pursuit of this objective the Council has promoted projects of international cooperation between library groups, and has facilitated the travel of American and foreign librarians and archivists in the execution of such projects. During the past year a project of unusual promise was presented for improving relations between the archives of the world and their potential users.

Archives, as primary sources for the writing of history, are most important to the researcher. Access to them has often been difficult due to illiberal restrictions on use and copying. Recently there have been indications that the trend may be toward greater restrictiveness rather than greater liberality. In the hope of countering this trend the National Archives of the United States has invited the International Council on Archives to hold, as its first meeting in the United States, an Extraordinary Congress in Washington in May 1966 to discuss the topic “Archives for Scholarship: Encouraging Greater Ease of Access.” The Council has made a grant to the National Archives Trust Fund Board to assist the meeting. Approximately 150 leaders of the world archival community, including some 25 from Latin America and 60 from the United States and Canada, are expected to attend the four-day meeting. The International Council on Archives was established in June 1948 and has since functioned under the auspices of Unesco.

A National Plan for the Preservation of Deteriorating Library Research Materials. Following publication of the results of the investigations of W. J. Barrow indicating that most of the books published in the United States in the first half of this century will be unusable at its end, the Association of Research Libraries established a Committee on the Preservation of Research Library Materials. The first questions put by the Committee asked: how much deteriorating material is there in

the libraries of the country, what is its distribution by date and place of origin, and what is the rate of its deterioration? To find answers to these questions the Council made it possible for the Committee to commission certain statistical studies in 1961-1962. The results, which have been published, indicate that the corpus of material (in single copy) in American libraries requiring preservative measures amounts to some three billion pages.³¹

As a next step, in 1962 the Council made a grant to assist the Association to develop an overall plan for the preservation of this material.³² Mr. Gordon R. Williams, Director of the Midwest Inter Library Center (since renamed the Center for Research Libraries) was commissioned to investigate. His report was rendered in the Fall of 1964 and was presented to the Association at its meeting in January 1965.³³

The report balances the prospective merits of preservation by means of microfilm copy against those of extending the life of the original by deacidification and storage at reduced temperatures. But the report is concerned not only with preservation; it insists upon continuous availability, and—to make this possible—it envisages photocopying programs to supply facsimiles upon demand and the originals also when required for consultation.

Central to the proposal is its execution by a national agency that will represent the research libraries, with responsibility for assuring “the physical preservation for as long as possible of at least one example of every deteriorating record, and that will make copies of these records available to any library when required.” The costs estimated for executing the program approximate a million dollars a year over an extended period.

It is a bold program which has been suggested, bold because requiring expensive and exacting measures, but not less expensive or exacting than would be the foreseeable disappearance of the records of the past and present, as the monuments at Abu

³¹ V: 21; VI: 22-23.

³² VII: 23.

³³ Association of Research Libraries, Committee on Preservation of Research Library Materials: *The Preservation of Deteriorating Books: An Examination of the Problem with Recommendations for a Solution*, prepared for the Committee by Gordon Williams, n. p., 1964. 33 p. 28 cm.

Simbel are disappearing under the rising waters of the Aswan Dam.

Preservation of Library Materials — The W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. Previous reports have recorded the construction of this laboratory in 1961 in attractive space provided by the Virginia State Historical Society, and its progress in these quarters.³⁴ During the past year the Laboratory was principally concerned with the following:

- Continued testing of old papers, working back decade by decade from 1900 to ascertain just what has happened to the papers of the past and if possible why. At the close of the year the decades of the nineteenth century were nearly completed.
- Investigation of the factors affecting the permanence/durability of polyvinyl acetate adhesives with a view to identifying an adhesive suitable for “perfect binding” for library use. A final report was sent to the press just before the close of the year (see p. 33).
- Investigation of the effect of storage temperature upon the permanence of paper (the first of a prospective three-year study).
- Investigations looking to the establishment of performance standards for library binding (the second of a three-year project, conducted under contract with the Library Technology Project of the American Library Association).

During the year two additions were made to the Laboratory’s report series *The Permanence/Durability of the Book* which had been established the previous year. The first of these constitutes an important record of test data found for naturally aged papers.³⁵ Since all prediction of prospective permanence/durability must be based upon actual experience of natural aging, this data is of fundamental importance. The other addition to the series reported on the development of an aerosol method for deacidifying paper materials, the investigation for which was concluded in 1963.³⁶

³⁴ VI: 21-22; VII: 20-23; VIII: 29-32.

³⁵ W. J. Barrow: *Test Data of Naturally Aged Papers*. Richmond, Virginia: W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, 1964. 79 p. (Permanence/Durability of the Book — II).

³⁶ W. J. Barrow: *Spray Deacidification*. Richmond, Virginia: W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, 1964. 62 p. (Permanence/Durability of the Book — III). See also VII: 20-21.

Another publication recorded the results of a limited investigation by the Laboratory of file folders suitable for archival use.³⁷

Still other publications by Mr. Barrow and by Mr. Lee E. Grove of the Council's staff have continued to make the work of the Laboratory known.³⁸

Russian Studies in Preservation of Library Materials. With the cooperation of the National Science Foundation, the Council was able to arrange for the translation and publication this past year of two volumes of Russian studies in the field of preservation of library materials.³⁹ The English-language editions were prepared by the Israel Program for Scientific Translations for the Office of Technical Services, U.S. Department of Commerce. A variety of subjects in connection with the care of manuscripts and books are discussed in the essays, which are also interesting because the approach rarely is the same as the American.

Improved Archival Containers. The purpose of the common practice of putting records into boxes is, of course, to protect them. But if the boxes are not in themselves an effective shield, or if they perhaps even induce deterioration of the material, the purpose is thwarted. At the suggestion of Leon deValinger, the State Archivist of Delaware, the Council in 1961 entrusted to the Library Technology Project administration of a project to develop a container having improved characteristics in low acidity, insect repellancy, and fire and mold resistance.⁴⁰ Co-sponsors of the project were the American Library Association and the Public Archives Commission of Delaware. The Library

³⁷ W. J. Barrow: Archival File Folders. *The American Archivist*. 28: 125-128, January 1965.

³⁸ W. J. Barrow. Deacidification and Lamination of Deteriorated Documents, 1938-63. *The American Archivist*. 28: 285-90, April 1965. Lee E. Grove: Paper Deterioration—An Old Story. *College and Research Libraries* 25: 365-374, September 1964.

³⁹ Moscow. Publichnaia biblioteka. *Otdel gigeny i restavratsii knig*. Collection of materials on the preservation of library resources. Sbornik materialov po sokhrannosti knizhnykh fondov. Translated from Russian [by B. Toker and IPST staff] Jerusalem, Israel Program for Scientific Translations; [available from the Office of Technical Services, U. S. Department of Commerce, Washington, c. 1964] 258 p.

New methods for the Restoration and Preservation of Documents and Books (Novye metody restavratsii knig). Editor-in-chief N. Ya. Solechnik. Translated from Russian. Jerusalem, Israel Program for Scientific Translations; [available from the Office of Technical Services, U. S. Department of Commerce, Washington, c 1964.] 130 p.

⁴⁰ VI: 23-24.

Technology Project contracted with the Institute of Paper Chemistry, Appleton, Wisconsin, to conduct the investigation. The project has been completed and a report published.⁴¹

Control of acidity in the container board was found to be a relatively simple matter. Insect repellancy was found to be more difficult and it finally appeared that the most effective method is in good housekeeping. The development of a fire resistant container was also found to offer difficult problems, with some methods resulting in the negation of other virtues. The use of plastic coatings and the lamination of the container board with thin aluminum foil were found to improve resistance to mold (fungi). However, the cumulation of the protective measures added excessively to the cost of manufacture, and in consequence no commercial runs of the improved container board were effected as originally proposed.

Bookbinding — An Adhesive for "Perfect Binding." "Perfect binding" is typically employed for telephone directories, paperback books and certain periodicals; instead of being sewn, the sheets are trimmed at the spine and held together exclusively by adhesive. For library use the method offers the possibility of certain advantages over other methods — specifically, less cost than hand-sewing but greater openability of the bound book than with oversewing. However, a prerequisite for seriously considering it for library work is that the adhesive used should have a prospect of greater permanence/durability than has come to be associated with the animal glues and synthetic adhesives usually met in the commercial "perfect binding."

Although the lack of precise data regarding the natural aging of adhesives has deterred many from investigations involving predictions of the permanence/durability of these materials, the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory finally yielded to urgings to attempt such an investigation. This has, in consequence, been proceeding for the past three years.⁴² While this investigation has relied heavily upon the techniques developed by Mr. Barrow for his studies of permanence/durability in paper, it has also required new test procedures and equipment, as well as the imaginative use of the available data regarding natural aging, despite the preponderance of unknown characteristics.

⁴¹ Gladys T. Piez: Archival Containers — A Search for Safer Materials. *American Archivist* 27: 433-438, July 1964.

⁴² VII: 21-2; VIII: 30.

CHINESE BOOKS FOR WESTERN SCHOLARS. The Chinese Materials and Research Aids Service Center, in Taiwan, has processed more than 200,000 volumes for libraries and individual students in 21 countries during the past year. Above: Mr. Ts' ai Ch'iu-t'ien selects books to fill an order. Below: Miss Liu prepares a new periodic booklist, while Mr. Lin Chiu-hsiung checks the consolidated index for bibliographic data in response to a library's inquiry. The (author, title, subject, publisher) index includes more than 60,000 cards and took a year to complete.

To make a long story short, during the past year the investigation appeared to have reached its goal, and before the end of the fiscal year a report was sent to the press.⁴³

Acquisition of Chinese Research Materials. One feature of the boom in Far Eastern studies since World War II is the pressure of research libraries to build collections in this field. This is reflected in a recent survey of fifty North American collections. Some twenty of them, it was found, had been built up in the past half dozen years, and the total resources in Far Eastern languages had increased by a half million volumes since 1950. During the past year alone collections had increased by nearly two hundred thousand volumes at a cost of some half million dollars.

Many of the works needed by the universities are not only expensive to begin with, but out of print and scarce besides. To alleviate this situation a Chinese Materials and Research Aids Service Center has been established in Taipei, Taiwan, under the auspices of the Association for Asian Studies. The Council has made a grant to the Association to assist the Center in getting started. Under the direction of an American scholar, Dr. Robert L. Irick, the Center is encouraging republication in Taiwan of out-of-print works, providing information to libraries on what is available on the Taiwanese market, preparing bibliographical and research aids, and acting as an agent in securing books and periodicals. It did more than \$120,000 worth of business during its first eight months operation and the volume is growing.

Depository Copies of Non-GPO U.S. Documents. The Depository Library Act of 1962 provided for the distribution to depository libraries of Federal publications printed elsewhere as well as in the Government Printing Office. The House Appropriations Committee, however, withheld funds for this purpose for fiscal year 1964 on the grounds that the significance of the non-GPO material is doubtful; but the Committee asked for information on this point. As a result the Interdivisional Committee on Public Documents of the American Library Association made plans for listing significant non-GPO documents.⁴⁴ With assistance from the Council a catalog

⁴³ W. J. Barrow: *Polyvinyl Acetate (PVA) Adhesives for Use in Library Bookbinding*. Richmond, Virginia: W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, in press. (Permanence/Durability of the Book — IV)

⁴⁴ VIII: 21-22.

was compiled by the chief of the Exchange and Gift Division of the Library of Congress, listing some 1500 imprints chiefly of 1963 and 1964. This was published in February 1965.⁴⁵

Photocopying - Book Copying Devices. The Library Technology Project's first separate publication on this subject, Mr. William R. Hawken's *Photocopying from Bound Volumes* was issued in 1962. It has been kept up to date by supplements, each reporting and appraising new equipment.⁴⁶ In October 1964 a third supplement evaluated six new devices.⁴⁷

Microstorage in Crystals. An investigation of the recording, storage at high resolution and reading out of graphic information, utilizing the crystal color center phenomenon in certain crystals, has been reported previously.⁴⁸ This past year the Carson Laboratories, of Bristol, Connecticut, brought to a close their work on a second contract for the Council on this project. Though much has been learned from the investigation, it appeared that the hoped-for advantage for library work — namely an inexpensive method of storing and recovering information — will not soon be available. A paper to be presented by Dr. Arthur N. Carson, president of the Laboratories, at the International Symposium on Color Centers, to be held at the University of Illinois in October 1965, is expected to embody some of the findings.

An Inexpensive Micro-Projector. The previous annual report recorded the engineering design study for an inexpensive micro-projector commissioned from Photo Devices, Inc., of Rochester, N. Y.⁴⁹ The study was completed and a prototype constructed. It is truly portable (suitcase style, approximately 15 pounds in weight); it has many good features and is designed to be sold at the low price of approximately \$50.

Telefacsimile Between Libraries. The prospect of nearly-instantaneous transmission of facsimiles of printed pages or

⁴⁵ Jennings Wood: *United States Government Publications, A Partial List of Non-GPO Imprints, Prepared under the Direction of the Interdivisional Committee on Public Documents of the American Library Association.* Chicago: American Library Association, 1964. 86 p.

⁴⁶ VIII: 34.

⁴⁷ William R. Hawken: *Photocopying from Bound Volumes, Supplement No. 3.* Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, 1964. 40 p. III.

⁴⁸ VII: 27-28; VIII: 26-27.

⁴⁹ VIII: 24.

other records has always held a fascination for libraries. Yet the experimental demonstrations which have been held from time to time (including those at the Library of Congress, National Library of Medicine and National Institutes of Health (1953), the University of Virginia (1957), the Franklin Institute and the General Electric Company (1963) and the Manchester College of Science and Technology (1963), and the Marconi Company (1964) all indicate that the elements for successful application are difficult to define and assemble.⁵⁰

The Council's initial concern with this matter was in its support of a closed-circuit television link between the central and departmental libraries at the University of Virginia in 1956. Later the Council commissioned a review of available equipment and channels from a Boston engineering firm, Image Instruments, Inc.⁵¹ However, it concluded that telefacsimile, at the distances found in urban communities, cannot compete in cost and only unimportantly in convenience with a photocopying and messenger service, while for longer distance it is difficult to justify the differential in cost over that of photocopying and postal service. Accordingly, the Council has awaited a development which would reduce the cost both of the terminal equipment and of the channel, yet provide an acceptably rapid facsimile.

Recently a device has been developed which employs a telephone handset as part of the terminal equipment and which can use as a channel a telephone circuit of even the lowest capacity ordinarily found. Although with such a channel transmission is admittedly slow (six minutes per 8.5 x 11-inch page) yet its cost is low even over long distances. The Council has made a small grant to enable the library of the University of Nevada at Reno to experiment with this system over the long distances which separate its library from many of its own users and from other libraries.

⁵⁰ Scott Adams: Facsimile for Federal Libraries, *Special Libraries* 44: 169-172, May-June 1953. Roger Bristol: Closed Circuit Television Experiment in a University Library, *Southeastern Librarian* 8: 11-14, Spring 1958. Pennsylvania Libraries Experiment with Electronic Facsimile System *Library Journal* 88: 1848-49, May 1, 1963; Remote Controlled Reading: *Manchester Guardian Weekly* 9, July 4, 1963; Document Transmission by Closed Circuit Television, *Aslib Proceedings* 16: 230-1, August 1964.

⁵¹ I: 22-23; VII: 23.

III. ADMINISTRATIVE ARRANGEMENTS

(Here are discussed projects which seek the improvement of those arrangements by which the means both of bibliographic and of physical access to sources of information are brought to the service of the reader. Examples are projects for the improved planning of library buildings, for the training of staff, for standardizing and testing of library materials and supplies, and for exploration of legal problems affecting photocopying.)

American Library Laws. The second edition of *American Library Laws*, a 1,247-page volume published in 1943, had long been obsolete when in 1962 the Council made a grant for the preparation of a new edition.⁵² The compilation has been completed by Dr. Alex Ladenson, Assistant Librarian, Chicago Public Library, and a member of the Illinois Bar, working under the general direction of the Legislative Committee of the American Library Association. A 1,559-page book printed by photo-offset, it includes all laws pertaining to libraries of the Federal Government, the 50 states, and the territories and dependencies in effect as of December 31, 1962.

It is planned that funds recovered from sales of the new third edition will be used to produce biennial supplements and a revised basic volume ten years hence. Since publication of the third edition, the first supplement has appeared, updating the basic work with laws added, amended, or repealed between January 1, 1963 and December 31, 1964. Like the basic volume, it was edited by Dr. Ladenson and issued by the Publishing Department of the American Library Association.⁵³ Together the two volumes reflect the many significant changes which have occurred in American library laws during the past twenty odd years.⁵⁴ Not only have the general laws governing public libraries been wholly rewritten in some states but in some jurisdictions new concepts of librarianship have been introduced, while elsewhere interstate or local interjurisdictional agreements for library cooperation have required a new

⁵² VII: 32.

⁵³ Alex Ladenson, ed.: *American Library Laws*, Third Edition, Chicago: American Library Association, 1964, vii, 1,559 p. *First Supplement, 1963-1964*, 1965, viii, 216 p.

⁵⁴ Alex Ladenson: Twenty Years of Library Legislation. *ALA Bulletin*, 125-131, February 1965.

legal basis. Federal or state aid to libraries has also necessitated new legislation.

Archival Administration in the States. The Society of American Archivists reached the conclusion several years ago that the most helpful undertaking for effecting improvement of state archival administration would be a survey which would describe the situation in plain but authoritative language, and make specific recommendations. A grant from the Council in 1961 made it possible for the Society to commission Dr. Ernst Posner, Professor Emeritus of History and Archives Administration of the American University, to perform the survey and to prepare a report.⁵⁵ Dr. Posner's book-length study of archival arrangements in the 50 states and the Commonwealth of Puerto Rico was published in the fall of 1964.⁵⁶

After a review of existing state archival programs leading to the conclusion that few are adequate, Dr. Posner provides a statement of standards that was formulated in consultation with an advisory committee of five distinguished archivists and with the Committee on Professional Standards of the Society of American Archivists. The statement covers such matters as: legal authority, budgetary requirements, personnel, and facilities of the state agency; the agency's functions, including control over the disposal of useless records, the arrangement and description of permanently valuable records, reference service, photographic reproduction and publication activities, and care and preservation of local records; and, finally, the role of the state archival agency in records management.

Dr. Posner's report was intended to be an "action document" and has fully met the expectation. Developments since its publication are summarized in the Appendix.⁵⁷

Library Statistics. Although American library statistics have been published in one form or another since the Smithsonian Institution issued the first important compilation of the kind in 1850, the fact is that for want of an adequate single source some 140 separate services have come into being, each with its own special base or viewpoint.

⁵⁵ VI: 36-37.

⁵⁶ See Ftn. 5.

⁵⁷ Pages 48-51 *in/ra*.

To make a single adequate source of such statistics possible, decisions were needed as to the kinds of statistical information required, together with definitions and standards. As a result of consultations between the U.S. Office of Education, the American Library Association and the Special Libraries Association, Mr. Joel Williams of the Educational Statistics Branch of the U.S. Department of Health, Education and Welfare was in 1963 given a leave of absence to prepare, under grants from the Council and the National Science Foundation, and with the assistance of an advisory committee, a handbook of accepted practice for the gathering and presentation of library statistics.⁵⁸

During the past year the handbook was completed and has been sent to the press. It is expected to be published by the American Library Association early in fiscal year 1966.

Among those active in the project was Dr. Frank L. Schick, Office of Education, both in his official capacity and as chairman of the Subcommittee on Library Statistics of the Sectional Committee on Library Work and Documentation of the American Standards Association. The Council assisted Dr. Schick to attend, as representative of the American organization, the meeting of the International Standards Association in Budapest in October 1964, where coordination of library statistics was on the agenda. As a result, a working group was formed comprising representatives from twelve countries. Unesco, and the International Federation of Library Associations to draft an international standard for library statistics.

Work Simplification for the Small Library. When the American Library Association's Small Libraries Project was planned in 1960, it omitted from its series of 16 manuals one on work simplification, although this was in the original design of the project as conceived by Mr. Joseph L. Wheeler, the director emeritus of the Enoch Pratt Free Library.⁵⁹ Consequently, at a later date, in collaboration with the Graduate School of Library Service of Drexel Institute of Technology, in Philadelphia, he developed plans for a study which would result in such a manual. The Council in 1963 made a grant for the purpose.⁶⁰

⁵⁸ VII: 31-32.

⁵⁹ V: 26-27; VII: 33-4.

⁶⁰ VII: 34.

This past spring the project was completed with publication of the manual.⁶¹

The manual was prepared by Mr. Donald D. Dennis, Librarian of Cedar Crest College, Allentown, Pennsylvania and is addressed to libraries serving communities with a population of 25,000 or less. It proceeds on the premise "that the benefits derived from any activity undertaken by the staff of the library should outweigh the time and expense involved." Thus, good service, not mere inexpensiveness in material and staff costs, is the basic criterion in the recommendations and instructions for simplifying work. After a chapter describing methods of analyzing an activity so as to simplify the procedures required to effect it, the manual discusses each of the principal operations of day-to-day library work with a separate chapter on finances and statistics. Three appendixes give closer attention to the costs of cataloging and book preparation and include a buying guide. Ten thousand copies of the report have been distributed to small libraries throughout the 50 states — in 49 instances through state agencies and in the other instance directly.

A Data Processing Handbook. Lack of experience on the part of many librarians with the techniques of data processing and their incomplete understanding of the economic and operational significance of these techniques constitute a principal obstacle to the exploitation of data processing in libraries. In consequence the Council has made a grant to the University of California to enable Professor Robert M. Hayes, Associate Director of the Institute of Library Research and a member of the faculty of the School of Library Service at the University of California at Los Angeles, to work with collaborators on a handbook which will attempt to close this gap.

The plan for the book calls for the orderly presentation of the existing diffused material relating to data processing in libraries so as to give a background of knowledge about mechanization which will provide a basis for communication between the librarian and the data processing specialist. As visualized, three sets of characteristics will be related to each

⁶¹ Donald D. Dennis: *Simplifying Work in Small Public Libraries.* [Philadelphia:] Drexel Institute of Technology, 1965. v, 80 p. (Drexel Library School Series).

other: the characteristics of the library systems, of the equipment, and of the data processing facilities available to the library. Plans call for three sections: one on systems and techniques, one on equipment, and one on library system analysis and evaluation.

The Library Technology Project was established in 1959 as a headquarters activity of the American Library Association. The Council this past year again continued its support.⁶² LTP has established its usefulness, and in its current budget the Association has provided for an ALA office for Research and Development of which LTP will serve as the cornerstone.

The purpose of LTP is to further library work through testing and evaluation of supplies and equipment, preparation of specifications, promotion of standards, development of new devices and techniques, and the conduct of an information service to libraries on these matters.⁶³ Hitherto this last has taken the form of reports in a column appearing in the *ALA Bulletin* and in *Special Libraries* and in separate publications. This past January, however, saw the beginning of a new bimonthly service published on a subscription basis and called *Library Technology Reports* to provide information about systems, equipment, and supplies. Despite its cost (\$100 per annum), as of June 30, 1965 there were 673 subscribers to this looseleaf service.

Some New LTP Projects. One LTP project initiated this past year is a study preliminary to developing *a book charging system for academic libraries*. The study will seek to identify the design characteristics for an improved charging system which will meet at least the minimum objectives of circulation control and achieve some economies.

The preparation of *a manual on floors and floor coverings for libraries* is still in progress.⁶⁴ Preparation of *a manual on carpet underlays* was begun this past year. The relationship of various underlays to carpet wear, resiliency, and durability are among the factors to be taken into consideration. Incidental to

⁶² III: 39; IV: 20-21; V: 27-28; VI: 34-36; VII: 38-39; VIII: 33-34.

⁶³ For a more detailed account of LTP, see Gladys T. Piez: *Library Technology Project—Today and Tomorrow*. *Libri* (Copenhagen) 14: 330-336, 1964. ———: *Library Technology Project: Past, Present, and Projected Future*. *The Library Quarterly* 35: 97-108, April 1965.

⁶⁴ VII: 39.

the inquiry has been the invention and construction of a testing device which simulates the effect of walking on carpet.

Some Completed LTP Projects. The study of *catalog card reproduction* was finished and a resulting manual was published this past year.⁶⁵

A report on *library-type record players*, published by LTP in 1962 and now obsolete, was superseded by a new report in which twelve record players are evaluated and rated.⁶⁶ Components, accessories and safety factors are also evaluated.

Mr. William R. Hawken's 1962 report on *photocopying from bound volumes* was likewise updated during the year, as reported on a previous page.⁶⁷

When the time comes for *moving books* from the old library building to a new one, some libraries prosaically call in the moving man, some college libraries call for volunteers from the student body, while the Denver Public Library wafted its books on a two-block long conveyor belt over the city's Civic Center. The whole problem of moving is dealt with in a monograph by Peter Spyers-Duran published this past spring.⁶⁸

Publication by LTP of an important report on *library insurance* in 1963 has been previously noted.⁶⁹ The book, which was the product of a careful study by a firm of insurance engineers, contained, among other features, a model insurance policy. After publication the American Library Association's Committee on Insurance for Libraries interested a leading insurance group in writing a policy similar to that in the book. At the end of the last fiscal year this Special Library Insurance policy of the Hartford Fire Insurance Company has been approved for writing in 39 states and the District of Columbia. Especially written for libraries, the policy can effect savings that

⁶⁵ See p. 25-26

⁶⁶ *Evaluation of Record Players for Libraries, Series II.* Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, 1964. [68 p.] Ill.

⁶⁷ See p. 36

⁶⁸ Peter Spyers-Duran: *Moving Library Materials.* Revised Edition. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, [1965]. vi, 63 p. Ill.

⁶⁹ VII: 29-31. *Protecting the Library and Its Resources. A Guide to Physical Protection and Insurance. Report on a Study Conducted by Gage-Babcock & Associates, Inc.* Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, [1963]. xv, 322 p. Ill.

were not possible when these institutions were included in a broader classification.

A study of the use of punched card electrical accounting machines in *circulation control* at Harvard, the University of California at Los Angeles and the IBM Research Center at Yorktown Heights, New York, has been completed and publication is planned. An evaluation of two similar systems in use in Europe has also been made.

One project, the proposed *manual on library furniture*⁷⁰ was indefinitely deferred when the plans were not executed as expected. Another project, the *improved newspaper stick*,⁷¹ in spite of the attentions of one of the country's best known engineering research firms, did not survive field testing and has been abandoned.

Student Use of Libraries in Washington. The enormous research library resources of the Washington area hide the fact that access to libraries is quite inadequate for certain classes of readers below the research level. This past year the Council made a small grant to the District of Columbia Library Association to enable its Committee on National Library Week to commission a preliminary study to recommend steps to rectify these inadequacies and to introduce a greater measure of coordination into the library systems of the area in the interest of student and other users. The study was conducted by Dr. Guy Garrison, Director of the Library Research Center, of the Graduate School of Library Science of the University of Illinois.⁷² Means are being sought to further its proposals.

⁷⁰ VII: 39.

⁷¹ V: 26.

⁷² Guy Garrison: *Proposal for a Study of Library Service to Students in the Greater Washington Area with Suggestions for Further Research.* [Washington, D. C.] District of Columbia Library Association, 1964. 14 l. 28 cm.

IV. PLANNING

Libraries and Automation — Meetings. In May 1963 a Conference on Libraries and Automation was held at the Airlie Foundation near Warrenton, Virginia, under the joint sponsorship of the Library of Congress, National Science Foundation, and the Council.⁷³ The working papers, which have contributed significantly to the understanding of the problems in this area, were published in October 1964.⁷⁴

In June 1964 a conference on automation and library planning was held at the University of Pittsburgh, under the chairmanship of Mr. Allen Kent, Director of the Knowledge Availability Systems Center and Professor, Graduate School of Library and Information Sciences. The Council made a small grant to assist the meeting, a principal purpose of which was to discuss the proposal of Dr. Stafford L. Warren, Special Assistant to the President of the United States, for a National Science Library System. Dr. Warren's proposal and the ensuing discussion are recorded in a report of the Conference published this past summer.⁷⁵

Junior College Libraries. In February 1964 the Council co-sponsored with the American Association of Junior Colleges a meeting in Washington, D. C., to discuss the problems of junior college libraries.⁷⁶ This past year the Council made a grant to the Association to hold a joint meeting at Mount San Antonio College, Walnut, California in May 1965 together with the American Library Association's Committee on Junior College Libraries. Plans were discussed for a national program to strengthen the nation's junior college libraries, less than ten per cent of which meet ALA standards for collections and less than twenty per cent of which meet the standards for staff.

The Federal Governmental Libraries. The circumstances which led the Council to support a study of the Federal libraries by the Brookings Institution have been recorded in previous

⁷³ VII: 40.

⁷⁴ See Ftn. 2.

⁷⁵ Allen Kent, ed.: *Library Planning For Automation, Based on the Proceedings of a Conference Held at the University of Pittsburgh, June 2-3, 1964*. Washington, D. C.: Spartan Books, Inc.; London: Macmillan and Company, Ltd. [1965]. ix, 195 p.

⁷⁶ VIII: 45.

annual reports.⁷⁷ A principal recommendation of the Brookings report was that there should be a Federal library council to assist in the coordination of these libraries.

Since then, the Library of Congress, working with the Bureau of the Budget and with other Federal libraries, has taken action to establish a Federal Library Committee, comprised of 18 members of which 12 are permanent, representing the Library of Congress, National Agricultural Library, National Library of Medicine, and each of the executive departments, while the other six, serving two-year terms, represent six independent Federal agencies chosen on a rotating basis.

The Committee seeks improved coordination and planning among the Government's research libraries. As a first step, task forces have been organized to study and make recommendations on such specific problems as inter-library loan practices among the Federal libraries, more efficient methods of acquisition, coordination of collecting policies, and aspects of automation.⁷⁸

The Department of the Interior has permitted its librarian, Mr. Paul Howard, to serve as executive secretary of the Committee, with an office at the Library of Congress.

The Council has made a grant to defray initial secretariat expenses of the Committee.

New York World's Fair — Conventional-Electronic Library. The "Library/USA" exhibit in the United States Pavilion at the New York World's Fair is a 7,000-square-foot library providing service and including both conventional library equipment and other equipment which has more recently been developed or which is still experimental.⁷⁹ The library is staffed on a rotating basis by selected reference librarians brought from all parts of

⁷⁷ III: 40-41; VIII: 44-45.

⁷⁸ The Establishment of the Federal Library Committee: A Symposium [by L. Quincy Mumford, Librarian of Congress, J. Lee Westrate, Bureau of the Budget, and Paul Howard, Librarian of the Department of the Interior] *D. C. Libraries* 36: 40-50, Summer 1965.

⁷⁹ "ALA's Library/USA is the first public demonstration of a Real-Time computer, with random access memory, performing non-numerical work in a library context and the first professional demonstration of how information may be communicated over future library and information networks." Joseph Becker: Demonstrating Remote Retrieval by Computer at Library/USA. *ALA Bulletin* 58: 822-824, October 1964.

the country and given training, to which the Council has contributed,⁸⁰ in the use of the new equipment. In the first year of the Fair there were more than 500,000 visitors to Library/USA; more than 210,000 bibliographies and essays were issued from the Library's computer, and more than 100,000 reference questions by visitors were answered.⁸¹ From April 21, when the Fair began its second and final year, to June 30, 1965, Library/USA attracted an estimated 450,000 visitors.

International Collaboration Between Archives. Late in 1964 two distinguished French archivists, M. François Dousset, Inspector General of the Archives of France, and M. Etienne Taillemite, Curator of Naval and Colonial Records in the Archives Nationales, visited library and archival institutions in Washington, Annapolis, Philadelphia and New York at the invitation of the Librarian of Congress and the Archivist of the United States, with assistance of a grant from the Council.⁸²

⁸⁰ VIII: 47-48.

⁸¹ The Bulletin Board *ALA Bulletin* 59: 164, March 1965. For a first-hand account of the first year: Floyd M. Cammack: Library/USA's First Season. *Ibid.* 59: 115-119, February 1965.

⁸² Visit of the French Archivists *The American Archivist* 28: 179, January 1965.

APPENDIX

THE ARCHIVES AND OFFICIAL RECORDS PROGRAMS OF THE STATES

Developments since the Publication of *American State Archives*⁸³

In September 1961 Dr. Philip M. Hamer, then President of the Society of American Archivists, brought to the Council a proposal for a study of state archival programs to be made by Dr. Ernst Posner, Professor Emeritus of History and Archives Administration of the American University. Three months later the Council made a grant to the Society for the purpose in the amount of \$42,000 (subsequently increased to \$45,897); in February 1962 an office for the Study was provided by the National Archives of the United States; and in the period from March 1962 to April 1963 Dr. Posner, as Director of the Study, visited the archival agencies (or, where they did not exist, the responsible officials) in each of the states except Alaska. (Puerto Rico, though not visited, was also included in the final report.) In March 1963 the report was accepted for publication by the University of Chicago Press; the first published copies of it, under the title *American State Archives*, were available at the meeting of the Society of American Archivists in Austin in October 1964, and by the end of June 1965, 1395 copies had been sold including 350 copies purchased by the Society for distribution to state archivists, legislators and other officials.

When making the grant the Council had expressed its hope that the Study would not be a mere academic inquiry but might result in an action document that could be used to promote remedial measures in States lagging in the protection of their records. A year and a half later it may be simply stated that the speed and extent of the response has exceeded the expectation.

When it is recalled that the earliest copies of the report were available only in October 1964 (the Council's copies were not received until mid-November) it is apparent that the developments which have since taken place (to the end of the past

⁸³ See p. 39 *supra*.

fiscal year) have been crowded into little more than six months. Actually, these developments consist in large part of enactments of the state legislatures during their sessions in the early months of 1965.

While this unusual concentration of progress must be ascribed to a number of causes, it can hardly be doubted that principal catalytic roles were served, first, by the initial visits of the Director of the Study (who went, as he says, not as minister plenipotentiary of the Society of American Archivists, but certainly as an envoy extraordinary), and, second, by the prompt publication of an informative, trenchant and pungent report, of which one archivist said to the author, "Your report has become our Bible."

There follows a compressed summary of the principal recent developments in state archival programs, almost entirely in the period since the publication of *American State Archives*.

Two states that previously had no archival programs enacted legislation for the administration of their records of permanent value: Maine (H.B. 768) created the office of State Archivist, and Missouri (H.B. 294) enacted a State Records Act. Arizona (H.B. 154) laid the basis for good records management as a prerequisite of better administration of its archives. California (S.B. 752) directed its Secretary of State to "establish a Document Preservation Shop and an Indexing Section to facilitate the indexing and preservation of the archives." Nevada (A.B. 360) created and appropriated for the Division of Archives in the Office of the Secretary of State. In Ohio, legislation (H.B. 631) was enacted and was awaiting the governor's signature at year's end. In Iowa, New Hampshire and Vermont important legislation was considered and nearly but not finally achieved passage.

In several states improved organization of the archival agency was effected. In Illinois the Archives Management Division was separated from the State Library. Arkansas authorized the appointment of a professional archivist for its Historical Commission. Additional professional archival positions were created in Indiana, Maryland, Minnesota, Pennsylvania, Tennessee, Vermont and Wisconsin. In Nebraska the dormant position of state archivist was reactivated and commendably filled. The adjustment of salaries of archivists (which in some cases were less than those of doorkeepers in

the legislature) was apparently influenced by the Study; there were increases, to give two examples, in Alabama and North Carolina.

The example of several states which have recently built or provided for the building of adequate archives buildings (such as Georgia, New Jersey, North Carolina and Pennsylvania) have no doubt been at least in part responsible for progress in this particular. California's archival facility was improved by the construction of a security vault; Iowa has provided for a State office building, the construction of which will release space for a records center and archives; in Louisiana the Capitol Improvement Budget provides for an archives and records center; a proposed bond issue would concentrate the State's archives in a \$12 million building for the Ohio Historical Society; Tennessee appropriated for an addition to its State Library and Archives to house the technical services; Wisconsin provided for a doubling of its storage space; Wyoming appropriated \$1,500 for planning a building for its State Archives and Historical Department.

Records centers have been established in Indiana and South Carolina.

The practice of involving the state archival agency in the records programs of the local subdivisions has gained ground. Kentucky has designated a Local Records Officer; New Mexico's archival agency has issued a County Records Manual; Tennessee authorized (S.B. 527) county public records commissions and directed the State agency to produce a county records manual.

Microreproduction has an important place in the preservation of records, but, unless it is part of a well-planned program, it can be wasteful and objectionable. Rhode Island, Texas and Washington have recently established microfilming programs as part of the overall activities supervised by the records management agencies.

Substantial progress has been made in making archival holdings known through the publication of guides, a need emphasized by the Study Director during his visitations as well as in his report. Following earlier examples in Maryland and Pennsylvania, guides have been published in North Caro-

lina (1963 and 1964), Illinois (1964), Puerto Rico (1964) and Nebraska (1965). A guide is in preparation in Wisconsin and one is being planned in Vermont. Accession-lists are being currently published by Pennsylvania and South Carolina.

As a final piece of evidence of progress in this field it may be mentioned that, as contrasted with 18 students enrolled in 1964 in the institute on archives administration at the American University, 44 were admitted in 1965, while 33 additional applicants had to be turned away.

The comments on the Study by heads of state archives programs indicate that its contributions cannot be measured merely by the short-term legislative action even though that resulted in much needed improvement, but rather by long-term legislative and executive concern for the preservation of records, and by the heightened professional purpose and confidence which very evidently followed upon the episcopal visitations of the Study Director. As a historian member of the Council has written in a review of the Study report, it "will go on working for the rest of us — and for good government and historical scholarship — into the indefinite future."⁸⁴

⁸⁴L. H. Butterfield: Study report. *American Archivist* 28: 263-6. April 1965.

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 9, 1965

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1965 and its expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES
AND FUND BALANCE

June 30, 1965

ASSETS

Cash		\$ 172,384
Investments:		
United States Treasury Bills, at cost plus discount earned (approximates market)	\$ 298,627	
Savings account, including earned interest for the year of \$43,044	1,138,009	1,436,636
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation in annual installments of \$1,000,000 (Note)		4,000,000
Deposits		499
		<u>\$5,609,519</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable (see accompanying statement)	\$ 956,820
Accounts payable and withheld taxes	3,598
Fund balance:	
Balance June 30, 1964	\$5,434,000
Deduct — Expenditures less income for the year (see accompanying statement)	784,899
Balance June 30, 1965 (Note)	4,649,101
	<u>\$5,609,519</u>

NOTE

The installment for the year ended June 30, 1965 was received on June 25, 1964. The installment for the year ending June 30, 1966 was received on July 1, 1965. The terms of the Grant from The Ford Foundation provide that \$200,000 annually is earmarked to assist the Council "to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel." At June 30, 1965 \$1,031,282 of the Fund balance is earmarked for this purpose. Also, \$754,983 has been appropriated for other specific grants and contracts and \$13,124 has been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts to be made at his discretion.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

For the Year Ended June 30, 1965

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects (see accompanying statement)	\$ 714,221	
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded (see accompanying statement)	28,496	\$ 685,725
General administrative expense:		
Compensation and employee benefits	125,007	
Rent	9,300	
Professional services	2,382	
Travel and meetings	8,570	
Furniture and equipment	4,452	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	15,003	164,714
		<u>850,439</u>

INCOME

From investments	<u>65,540</u>
Expenditures less income	<u><u>\$ 784,899</u></u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
 STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS
 AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1965

	Payable June 30, 1964	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1965
American Association of Junior Colleges					
Support of a meeting on junior college libraries		\$ 3,880		\$ 3,880	
American Association of Law Libraries					
A mechanized compilation of a list of legal subject headings			\$ 119	(119)	
American Council of Learned Societies					
Inquiry into the basis for planning scholarly photocopying projects			11,341	(11,341)	
American Library Association					
Completion of ALA Catalog Code	\$ 15,468	7,931		15,468	\$ 7,931
Foreign survey of the Dewey Decimal Classification	20,000			20,000	
Library Technology Project					
Development of performance standards for library bookbinding — Phase II	10,000			10,000	
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1964			22	(22)	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1964	70,950		684	70,266	
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1965	130,000			130,000	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1965	100,000			47,969	52,031
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1966		130,000			130,000
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1966		100,000			100,000
Publication of a book-selection service at the college library level	100,000			50,000	50,000
Scholarships for staffing ALA reference library at New York World's Fair 1964-1965	20,000			20,000	
Support of the ALA International Relations Office	40,207			17,710	22,497
American Library Association (co-sponsor with Association of Research Libraries)					
Preparation of a book on the planning of college/university library buildings	12,000				12,000
Assembly on the Library Functions of the States, Program Committee					
Assistance toward Third Meeting, Washington D. C., November 13-15, 1963			77	(77)	
Association of American Law Schools					
Preparation of book selection lists for law school libraries	27,000				27,000

	Payable June 30, 1964	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1965
Association for Asian Studies, Inc.					
Establishment of a Chinese materials and research aids service center in Taiwan		\$ 10,000		\$ 5,000	\$ 5,000
Association of Citizens Library of Washington (Pennsylvania)					
Experiment in public library home delivery of books			\$ 1,332	(1,332)	
Association of Research Libraries					
Survey of original cataloging performed in American research libraries (supplement)	\$ 5,000	900		5,900	
W. J. Barrow Laboratory					
Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relating to the preservation of books and other library materials	78,572	7,086	5,877	59,524	20,257
Bell & Howell Company					
Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography	14,090				14,090
Capital Graphic Systems, Inc.					
Specification-design study of lithographic duplicator for library catalog cards	5,000		20	4,980	
Carson Laboratories					
Demonstration of high density crystalline photo-storage	24,959			24,959	
Coordination of cataloging rules *	146		146		
The de Florez Company, Inc.					
Field test of automatic book-cradle/ page-turner	1,333				1,333
Working model of a book-copying cradle/press..	929				929
Working model of a catalog card duplicator	2,314				2,314
District of Columbia Committee for National Library Week, 1965					
Survey of student use of libraries in the Washington metropolitan area		1,500	192	1,308	
Documentation, Inc.					
Development of a portable inexpensive reader-printer for microcopies	33,000			23,000	10,000
Drexel Institute of Technology					
Preparation of a manual on work simplification in small libraries	21,095			21,095	
Expenses connected with the study of concepts and problems of libraries of the future *	4,383		4,033	350	
Expenses of testing a coordinate index to legal literature *	3,509			331	3,178
Harvey Mudd College					
Study of the bases, including the use of the techniques of automata, for providing the capability of a science library for academic- industry service			75	(75)	

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1964	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1965
Houston Fearless Corporation					
Delivery of a prototype of a step-and-repeat filmcard camera-processor		\$ 63,000			\$ 63,000
Indiana University Foundation					
Final development and testing of a camera for catalogers' use		4,000		\$ 4,000	
Infonics, Inc.					
Investigation of the creation of a machine- readable record of Library of Congress catalog data — Phase II	\$ 37,067			37,067	
Study of mechanization of filing rules		3,350			3,350
Intectron Incorporated					
Investigation of factors affecting high- reduction microphotography	733				733
International Business Machines Corporation					
Pilot project for conversion of National Union Catalog to machine-readable form		10,200			10,200
International Federation for Documentation. Secretariat, 31st Meeting and Congress, Washington, D. C., October 1965					
Support of Meeting	10,000			10,000	
Library of Congress					
Creation of a national union catalog of manuscript collections (supplement)	35,565				35,565
Development of Library of Congress classifi- cation for Anglo-American law			\$ 77	(77)	
Development of a national plan for scholarly photocopying			369	(369)	
Establishment of a center for the coordination of foreign manuscript copying		75,300			75,300
Establishment of a National Register of Microform Masters office and publication of first volume of information collected		35,000		17,500	17,500
Services of the U. S. Government Printing Office in connection with the investigation of the creation of a machine record of Library of Congress catalog data	5,000				5,000
Study of possibilities of mechanization in large research libraries	20,000				20,000
Support of the work of the Federal Library Committee		10,000		10,000	
Travel grant to enable Director and Assistant Director of the Archives of France to visit the United States			832	(832)	
Meeting to discuss a format for the conversion of bibliographic data to machine-readable form for computer processing *		5,000		4,611	389

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1964	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1965
Music Library Association					
Representation at meeting of International Cataloging Code Commission of the International Association of Music Libraries, 1965		\$ 628		\$ 628	
To record the holdings of American Libraries for inclusion in the International Inventory of Musical Sources	\$ 13,650			13,650	
National Archives and Records Service					
Assistance toward an extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives, Washington, D. C., 1966		35,500			\$ 35,500
Pan American Union					
Compilation and publication of a subject heading list in Spanish	12,500				12,500
Photo Devices, Inc.					
Construction of a prototype of a microfilm reader for libraries		3,500		3,500	
Publication of a book selection list — various *		126,125			126,125
Society of American Archivists					
Report on developments following publication of American State Archives		1,000		1,000	
A study of state archives (supplement)			\$ 8	(8)	
Vernon D. Tate					
Investigation of sheet microfilm			1,663	(1,663)	
United States Office of Education, Department of Health, Education and Welfare					
International standardization of library statistics		600		600	
The University of California					
Preparation and publication of a handbook on data processing for libraries		68,498			68,498
University of California at San Diego					
Experimental application of a computer to serial records maintenance in a university library			812	(812)	
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	24,600				24,600
University of Nevada					
An experiment in library application of telefacsimile		3,723		3,723	
University of New South Wales					
A study of alphabetical subject indexing		7,500		7,500	
University of Pittsburgh					
Conference on Automation and Library Planning, June 1964			817	(817)	
	<u>\$899,070</u>	<u>\$714,221</u>	<u>\$ 28,496</u>	<u>\$627,975</u>	<u>\$956,820</u>
* Council-administered project					

A C K N O W L E D G M E N T S

The picture of the scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the front cover, is taken from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . .*, Paris, 1581. The picture has appeared in previous annual reports of the Council, commencing with the Third in 1959. An old Chinese version was also reproduced in the Sixth Annual Report (1962).

The French version reproduced here at the front is from; *Recueil d'ouvrages curieux de mathématique et de mécanique, ou, Description du cabinet de Monsieur Grollier de Serviere . . .* Lyon, D. Forey, 1719. The Comte Nicolas Grollier de Servière, "Ancien Lieutenant Colonel d'Infanterie," graced the world from 1677 to 1745. The present picture is reproduced from a copperplate in a copy of his book in the Rare Book Division, Library of Congress. The pertinent text reproduces that of the original.

The pictures of the Chinese Materials and Research Aids Service Center, Taipei, Taiwan, Republic of China, (Mr. Dennis Chin, photographer), appear here by courtesy of the Center.

The pictures of the Termatex devices are reproduced by courtesy of Jonker Business Machines, Inc., Gaithersburg, Maryland.

This Ninth Annual Report was designed by the George Lohr Studio, Washington, and is printed on "Permalife," a stable and enduring paper produced by the Standard Paper Manufacturing Company, Richmond, Virginia.

Council on Library Resources.

Report. 1st-

1956/57-

Washington.

v. 23 cm. annual.

Report year ends June 30.

1. Library science—Research.

Z673.C96A15

020.624

58-915 rev

Library of Congress

